

Snore pre-detection: processing window size effects

Diego Munduruca Domingues
Biomedical Engineering Laboratory
Escola Politécnica
University of São Paulo (USP)
São Paulo, Brazil
 ORCID: 0000-0002-7711-1353

Henrique T. Moriya
Biomedical Engineering Laboratory
Escola Politécnica
University of São Paulo (USP)
São Paulo, Brazil
 ORCID: 0000-0002-1595-1779

Abstract— Snoring is a problem that affects a large part of the population and is usually associated with or indicative of other diseases, several of them are linked to sleep disorders such as apnea. Tools that automatically identify snoring, providing information to the patient and to the medical professional are very useful since it is possible to identify the problem and follow the progress of someone undergoing anti-snoring treatment. One of the tasks that this tool must perform is the identification of sound events. One technique that can be used for this involves the use of an adaptive threshold over a predefined length of the audio itself. This paper aimed to identify the behavior of the sound events identification (snoring and non-snoring) by varying the length of the audio chosen to calculate the threshold. When using small windows, a large number of events are detected. This value drops exponentially by increasing the size of the window until it reaches a plateau. Furthermore, not only the number of events that are not snoring are impact, but even the number of real snoring, which leads to the loss of the solution's sensitivity.

Keywords— *Snoring, Automatic Detection, Adaptive Threshold*

I. INTRODUCTION

Snoring is the noise generated from the upper airways' vibration [1], specifically from soft tissues like tongue, soft palate and pharyngeal wall [2]. In adult population, the prevalence of snoring is 20-40% [1]. By the age of 60, snoring affects 60% of men and 40% of women [6]. Snoring degrades the sleep quality not only to the snorer itself, but even may induce secondary sleep disorders to the roommates. Furthermore, it can be an indicative of several diseases, such as systemic arterial hypertension, coronary artery disease and sleep disorders. In most cases, snoring is the earliest symptom of obstructive sleep apnea (OSA) [3].

Currently, there are no specific drugs available to cure snoring, although there are some strategies and therapies available, for example CPAP (Continuous Positive Airway Pressure), mandibular advancement devices (MADs), palatal surgery [4] and even maintain healthy habits, such as decreasing weight. There is also the possibility of strengthening the muscles of the pharynx through exercises.

However, most of the times the therapeutic efficacy has been evaluated based on the patient's roommate report - which is usually inaccurate and subjective. The establishment of a tool that can more accurately inform how much a patient is snoring and even provide characteristics of these events, such as intensity, distribution and so on, could be beneficial. It is expected to provide a comparative assessment between the difference before and after anti-snoring therapies and improve the treatment [2].

Some solutions have already been proposed to solve this problem. In general, these tools have two main phases: obtaining the events, where it is identified in which instants of the recorded audio may exist snoring; and the classification of the obtained events phase, which different noises such as breaths, coughing and noise are eliminated.

To accomplish the identification phase, one of the most traditional ways is to select the moments when the audio has an intensity bigger than a certain threshold. Some authors prefer to set a fixed threshold value - which can be a problem, since snores of the same person and, especially, snores of different people may have different intensities, with different standards. Even the sensitivity of the recording device and the distance placed from the patient, can vary between users. Thus, a possible solution for this is to use an adaptive threshold, calculated over stretches with predetermined duration, which will be called from here as window.

The duration of the window affects the event's identification, because sometimes the calculated threshold tends not to adapt to all events. In this way, if the window is too large, some low intensity events may end up not being identified. This situation is solved by using smaller windows, as they tend to adapt individually to each event (as shown in figure 1 in the methodology section).

Therefore, the purpose of this work is to identify the event detection behavior (snores and non-snores) by varying the window length and, thus, to analyze the impact of this variation on the solution's sensitivity.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

During the polysomnography (PSG) of ten patients, 5 males and 5 females, aged 44-64 years, the entire patient's audio nighttime were also recorded at the Sleep Laboratory of the Heart Institute of the Clinical Hospital of the Faculty of Medicine of the University of São Paulo. This research was approved by the ethics committee of the same institution (CAEE: 70485317.0.0000.0068).

To perform the recording, Android mobile (Samsung Galaxy J5) were used with an application developed by ourselves to record audio in WAV format, sampling frequency of 8 kHz and resolution of 16 bits per sample. The application doesn't perform any pre-processing on the recordings. The mobile was positioned less than one meter from the patient's head. The recording started before the patient was asleep, and it only ended in the next morning upon waking.

An algorithm was developed to capture the audio events. It calculates a threshold value based on pre-defined audio

lengths. These lengths were varied from 10 to 200 seconds, incrementing 10 seconds at a time. To detect each event, the following methodology was adopted: whenever this threshold was exceeded, the beginning and the end of an event were listed. In the figure 1, the graphs show examples of thresholds calculated from 60 seconds (figure 1a) and 20 seconds (figure 1b) windows. The threshold was calculated from the technique developed by Otsu et al [5].

The objective of Otsu et al was to develop a method of segmentation of gray scale images in two classes (e.g. background and objects) obtaining a threshold value that maximizes the separability between the two classes. The within-class variance is calculated as:

$$\omega_0\omega_1(\mu_1 - \mu_0)^2 \quad (1)$$

where: 0 and 1 is the two considered classes, ω is the probability of class occurrence and μ is the class mean level.

In our case, instead of having a grayscale image with two groups representing background and object, we have an audio power signal in which the two sets of data are the events of low intensity (background noise, predominantly) and events of more high intensity (snoring, conversation, cough, etc.).

Fig. 1. Adaptive thresholds with different windows lengths. In a), 60 seconds window was used and 4 events were unidentified because they did not exceed the threshold (in blue). In b), with a window of 20 seconds, all events were found.

Among all the events obtained, only those with duration between 0.5 milliseconds and 2 seconds were chosen for analysis, because, as indicated in the literature [6] [7], snores usually have duration within this range. In addition, events separated by a timeframe less than 0.5 milliseconds were merged and counted as a single event.

A. Audio Preprocessing

The adaptive threshold was calculated on the audio signal power, because in this way it is possible to decrease the number of samples, keeping the envelope of the positive part (figure 2). The power was calculated from the quadratic sum of the raw audio signal in a duration of 0.25 seconds, with 50%

overlaps on each stretch. These values were chosen after a few attempts, in which it was observed that the sound events were better highlighted from the background noise.

Fig. 2. Calculation of signal power. In a), raw audio signal. In b), signal power.

B. Analysis

In order to obtain the results, the event detection algorithm was used in the audios of each patient, and then, the number of total events obtained from each window was listed. Therefore, it was possible to observe the impact on the number of events identified by varying the window size.

Subsequently, the intention was to analyze the impact of this change in the obtention of snores itself, without considering events classified as non-snoring. In this way, 15 minutes of the audio of each patient with a high quantity of snores were chosen for comparison. These excerpts were fully heard, taking note of the position in time and the classification (snoring, breathing or noise) of each event. To apply the developed algorithm in these audios, three window sizes were chosen, representative of small, medium and large windows (respectively, 15, 60 and 180 seconds).

III. RESULTS

Figure 3 shows a graph of the number of events obtained by varying the window size, for the whole audios of the 10 patients. Curves with shape close to decreasing exponentials were obtained, as observed. Thus, at the beginning of each curve, it can be noted a peak in the amount of events detected, which decay as the window size increases; at a certain point, the amount of events reaches a minimum value within the analyzed range, with little variations regardless the window growth.

Fig. 3. Number of events (snoring and non-snoring) detected in an entire audio nighttime from 10 patients varying window size from 20 to 200 seconds.

The average number of events detected using a window of 15 seconds was 4596; for a window of 60 seconds, 3657 events were found; and, for a window of 180 seconds, 3335 events.

In the following table, the average percentage of unidentified snores for the three types of windows is presented, considering audios with 15 minutes. The number of not identified snores increased by 9 times when using a medium window and 15 times when using large windows, both in comparison to the small window.

TABLE I.

	Windows		
	<i>Small (15 seconds)</i>	<i>Medium (60 seconds)</i>	<i>Large (180 seconds)</i>
Average percentage of unidentified snores	0,35%	3,06%	5,36%

Fig. 4. Average percentage of unidentified snores for 3 window sizes (15, 60 and 180 sec-onds). These values refer to 15-minute audios with high nocturnal snoring in each of the 10 patients.

IV. CONCLUSION

The analysis of the number of events obtained by applying different window sizes (figure 3) showed that the number of events detected drops exponentially as the window size increases. From the result obtained, the three sizes of windows used to represent small (15 seconds), medium (60 seconds) and large (180 seconds) windows were chosen to be applied to the 15 minutes audios in order to investigate the impact on the detection of snoring itself.

Between the small window and the medium window, the amount of events obtained fell from 4596 to 3657 - a fall of 20.43%. Meanwhile, the number of undetected snores increased from 0.35% to 3.06%. Between the small window and the large window, the amount of events obtained dropped from 4596 to 3335 - a fall of 27.43% - and the number of undetected snores increased from 0.35% to 5.36%. It can be concluded that it was not only the non-snores and noises that

are no longer identified, as the window size increases; along with the fall in the number of events, there was also a fall in the number of snores found.

Thus, it was concluded that choosing small windows increases the sensitivity of the solution, since less snoring would be no longer identified. However, using small windows and obtaining a greater number of events may not be a good solution considering that later it will be used some classification method that has an associated error. The published literature indicates that classification methods, such as neural networks, have accuracy around 80-90% [4] [8]. In this way, a high number of false positives can be found when the classification fails, identifying non-snores event like snore leading to a reduction of the solution specificity.

On the other hand, using very wide windows is also not a good idea, because as we have seen, the number of events detected can decrease considerably, can cause lower intensity snores to be undetected. In addition, in a situation where it is prohibitively to record the entire patient's audio nighttime, whether for privacy or technical properties of the device, each stretch must be processed while the audio data remains in RAM memory. This way, the larger the window size, the more impact it will have on the performance of the device.

Therefore, a window size should be chosen in order to best match what is expected from the snore identification tool's performance. If it is necessary that the sensitivity be high, it is advisable to use short windows. On the other hand, if the solution needs to have a better specificity, should be considered to use long windows.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. Azarbarzin, Z. Moussavi, "Snoring sounds variability as a signature of obstructive sleep apnea," *Med. Eng. Phys.*, vol. 35, no. 4, pp. 479–485, 2013.
- [2] S. Akhter, U. R. Abeyratne, V. Swarnkar, "Characterization of REM/NREM sleep using breath sounds in OSA," *Biomed. Signal Process. Control*, vol. 25, pp. 130–142, 2016.
- [3] A. Yadollahi, Z. Moussavi, "Formant analysis of breath and snore sounds," *Proc. 31st Annu. Int. Conf. IEEE Eng. Med. Biol. Soc. Eng. Futur. Biomed. EMBC 2009*, pp. 2563–2566, 2009.
- [4] H. Hara, M. Tsutsumi, S. Tarumoto, T. Shiga, H. Yamashita, "Validation of a new snoring detection device based on a hysteresis extraction algorithm," *Auris Nasus Larynx*, vol. 44, no. 5, pp. 576–582, 2017.
- [5] N. Otsu, "A Threshold Selection Method from Gray-Level Histograms," *IEEE Trans. Syst. Man. Cybern.*, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 62–66, 1979.
- [6] H. Shin, J. Cho, "Unconstrained snoring detection using a smartphone during ordinary sleep," pp. 1–14, 2014.
- [7] F. K. Shiomi, I. T. Pisa, C. J. R. de Campos, "Computerized analysis of snoring in sleep Apnea Syndrome," *Braz. J. Otorhinolaryngol.*, vol. 77, no. 4, pp. 488–498, 2011.
- [8] B. Kang, X. Dang, R. Wei, "Snoring and apnea detection based on hybrid neural networks," vol. 2018-Janua, no. 61403276, pp. 57–60, 2018.